

Leveraging Social Media and Cloud Computing for Driving Public Participation in Government Decision Making

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Abstract— In recent times, social media have been increasingly used not only by general public, but also by the governments and planning professionals to gather public opinions, distribute information, and support e-participation in planning practices. This paper aims to propose a cloud based framework for the systematic, intensive, and centralized use of social media for government agencies to enhance government policy and decision making. The proposed architecture is based on a central cloud system, which publishes various types of policy-related content in multiple social media simultaneously, collects data from them and processes data on citizens' interactions involving sentiment analysis to generate leads. Preliminary findings are showcased, and three case studies are taken to check the effectiveness of proposed system in Nepal. Such a system provides decision support mechanism for the policy makers and aims to improve the effectiveness in public participation regarding transparency, reachability, accessibility, and workable solutions.

Keywords - Social Media, Cloud Computing, e-participation, Sentiment Analysis, Decision Making

I. INTRODUCTION

The potential benefits of public participation in government process include the promotion of open, transparent, inclusive, and fair decision-making processes. The first generation of e-participation was based on the development of numerous official digital spaces operated by government agencies such as their official websites, offering information on government activities, decisions, plans and policies to the citizens and providing capabilities for expressing their opinions and suggestions on various topics (Sanford & Rose, 2007). However, the usage and outcomes of this first generation of e-participation were below the initial expectations. It did not directly address citizens' daily problems and priorities and lacked transparency.

Traditionally, participation often selected a small number of representatives as stakeholders and required them to be present in a physical place at a particular time, resulting in many problems such as the lack of inclusion, and the inflexibility of participation. In recent years planners, and policymakers have turned their attentions toward digital tools and methods to overcome the problems of traditional participation methods. In particular, social media have been increasingly used in planning practices to support citizen participation. The

interactive and two-way communication features make them an effective tool for e-participation. 13.70 million people use some form of social media in Nepal (Kemp, 2022) which is 45.7% percent of the total population in Nepal. Study by Kepois (Kemp,2022) also suggested that social media users in Nepal is increased by 700 thousand between 2021 and 2022. Facebook is one of the most used social networking sites in Nepal having 12.30 million users in early 2022. This clearly states that social media usage is at all-time high in Nepal and can be a great means to drive public participation.

On the other hand, cloud computing is being prevalent in current technology and can be utilized to store, process, harness, compute and analyse the data from social media to generate policy making leads at low cost and high speed. With features such as on-demand access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources, rapid provisioning, pay-as-you, scalability, and minimal management effort, cloud computing has proven to be the tech industry greatest boon for government agencies to drive public participation even in remote areas where such manual provision of such infrastructure is very difficult and costly.

Current societies are more diverse and pluralistic in terms of culture, values, concerns, and lifestyles, and this makes public policy formulation problems 'wicked,' lacking clear and widely agreed definition and objectives, and having many stakeholders with different and heterogeneous problem views, values, and concerns (Rittel & Weber, 1973). This is where social media can be brought to drive participation as different citizens' group with respect to age, income, political orientations, lifestyle use them on a daily basis. With multiple content forms such as text, image, videos etc. from multiple providers like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter etc, social media with cloud computing power is the effective mechanism for increasing public participation in government decision making. This way, instead of inviting the citizens to interact with government in the official e-participation spaces in accordance with their rules and structures, government can go to the social media spaces where citizen prefer to have discussions, create content, and collaborate with others.

This paper contributes to this direction by exploring advanced forms of using and combining cloud computing

capabilities with different social media providers, with each of them being used by a different citizens' group, focusing on a different type of content (e.g., short text, long text, images, video). The proposed framework for this is based on the concept of a central cloud system which can publish various types of policy-related content to multiple social media simultaneously and also collect data from them on citizens' interactions (e.g., views, likes, comments, ratings etc). These interaction data will undergo in this central cloud system and various types of advanced processing such as data analytics, mining, AI driven sentiment analysis mining, simulation modelling and forecasting) in order to use these data to the highest possible extent for drawing synthetic conclusions and providing substantial support to government policy makers.

In the following sections relevant previous literature is reviewed, and the theoretical background of the proposed approach is presented. Then the proposed cloud framework is presented. We also look the architecture of the central cloud system, and the decision support subsystem of it. Some preliminary findings based on similar systems implemented at European Union are presented next, concerning the capabilities provided by the social media and the value generated by the proposed approach. We also analyse the growth of social media usage by politicians in Nepal taking two case studies. Finally, the conclusions are summarized, and future research directions are proposed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several success stories concerning the use of web 2.0 social media by government agencies. In Bertot et al. (2010) and Bertot, Jaeger, and Hansen (2012) the opportunities that web 2.0 social media offer to government agencies are classified into three main groups: i) democratic participation and engagement which concerns the use of social media technologies to engage the public in government policy making, fostering participatory dialogue and providing voice in discussions of policy development and implementation to more citizens' groups ii) public services co-production which focuses on governments and the public working jointly to develop, design, and deliver government services using social media, aiming to improve service quality, delivery, and responsiveness, and iii) crowdsourcing solutions and innovations which relies on seeking innovation by exploiting public knowledge and talent through social media interaction, in order to develop innovative solutions to big societal problems, and in order to facilitate this the government shares data with the to establish a base on which the citizens can reflect and innovate solutions.

According to Nam (2017) traditionally government agencies provide services to citizens, who consume them without questioning or taking part in decisions; on the contrary social media can drive and facilitate new government paradigms, in which citizens' roles change, so that government become a consumer to whom citizens provide information or even useful professional services. For this reason, Lukensmeyer and Torres (2018) suggest that such citizen-sourcing may change the government's perspective from viewing citizens as "users and choosers" of government services to "makers and shapers" of policies and decisions

Mergel, Schweik, and Fountain (2019) through an analysis of cases of successful use of cloud computing and social media in government reach the conclusion that cloud technologies might have stronger transformational effects on government than previous ICTs, driving significant changes at the organizational, cultural, technological, and informational changes. They mention that cloud computing enables in-depth collection of social media data, advanced processing capabilities, and generate highly useful data for policy makers at a fraction of a cost than traditional methods along with fast delivery. They state that this strong transformation potential is due to the lower setup barrier, and therefore the lower cost (for both government organizations and individual citizens), in comparison with the previous generations of ICT used in government (e.g., intra-organizational information systems, web 1.0 Internet,). These lower requirements allow a much quicker and easier deployment of cloud-based solutions to harness the true potential of social media data in decision making processes.

However, in Nepal, this great potential of social media is leveraged by government agencies only to a limited extent since only few government officials and units make use of social media for policy making and government purpose. Even a few that does this, usually only includes posting to a social media of some content, e.g., a political message in the form of a text, image, or video, and processing the corresponding user-generated content, e.g., comments or likes. A methodology for systematic, intensive, and centrally managed cloud framework for a wide analysis of appropriate various social media provider is missing. Our research aims to contribute to filling this gap.

III. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this section, we have described the theoretical foundations of the proposed framework of leveraging multiple social media by government agencies in a systematic and centrally managed manner, through a cloud system, for widening and enhancing public participation in public policy making:

a) the theory of wicked problems, b) the theory of software platforms and ecosystem, and c) the theory of cloud computing

A. Theory of Wicked Problems

The theory of wicked problems has been initially proposed by Rittel and Weber (1973). In particular, the societies have become more diverse and pluralistic in terms of culture, values and lifestyles, and this has made public policy problems 'wicked'; this implies that they lack clear and widely agreed definition and objectives, and are characterized by many stakeholders with different and conflicting views, perspective and objectives. The solution of these wicked public policy problems cannot be performed by experts through analytic techniques, but requires a two phases approach, which combines on one hand public participation, consultation and negotiation in order to formulate a shared definition of the problem in a first phase, followed by the use of analytic techniques by experts in a second phase on the other.

Having this well-defined problem as a base in a second phase we can proceed to a technocratic analysis by experts using mathematical optimization algorithms and advanced technology such as cloud computing. The emergence of the

web 2.0 social media creates huge opportunities for a wider and more inclusive application of the approach, which can involve many more citizens and social groups than previously. It enables a more intensive interaction among government and the multiple stakeholder groups affected by a new public policy. Social media, due to their ease of use and high popularity attracts large numbers of citizens from various diverse groups with regard to education, age, sex, ethnicity, religion, political beliefs, etc. It allow a wider and more inclusive discourse and synthesis of views on public policy problems that government faces, rapidly, efficiently and at a very low cost. This can result in better and more socially accepted and balanced public policies and decisions, considering the views, objectives, and knowledge of more citizens.

B. Theory of Software Platforms and Ecosystems

Software development today is increasingly based on pre-existing platforms that provides basic functionality, which are used for developing ‘modules’ that provide additional functionality and fulfills custom needs of specific user group. For instance, Apple’s iPhone operating system (iOS) serves as a platform for the development of its thousands of “apps. Another example can be Google Chrome where thousands of developers create extensions as add-ons and adds various functionalities.

The main concept in this software development paradigm according to Tiwana, Konsynski, and Bush (2016) is the ‘platform,’ which is defined as an extensible codebase of a software-based system, which provides the core functionality shared by the modules that connects to the platform in order to add functionality to it. While the ‘ecosystem’ is defined as the collection of the platform and the modules that have been developed based on it. The main objective of the research presented in this paper is to develop a central cloud platform that allows the exploitation of multiple social media for participative public policy making, hence the adoption of the paradigm is highly beneficial where we use the functionality of the targeted social media as platforms or foundation and based on them develop the functionality of all the cloud components needed to develop the central platform.

C. Theory of Cloud Computing

Cloud Computing is the use of hardware and software to deliver a service over internet. Cloud computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction (*NIST Cloud Computing Program - NCCP 2022*). This cloud model is composed of five essential characteristics, three service models, and four deployment models. Cloud computing systems satisfy many interesting characteristics that make them promise for future IT applications and services including their use for social media analysis. The National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) have defined five essential characteristics for cloud computing systems interaction (*NIST Cloud Computing Program - NCCP 2022*).

1) On-demand self-service

Cloud services such as CUP time, Storage, network access, server time, web applications etc can be allocated automatically as required by the consumers without any human interaction.

2) Cost effectiveness

Services provided by the cloud service providers are very cost effective if not free. The billing model is pay as per usage; there is no need to purchase the infrastructure and therefore lowers maintenance cost

3) Scalability

Scalability: the infrastructure of cloud computing is very scalable. Cloud providers can add new nodes and servers to cloud with minor modifications to cloud infrastructure and software.

4) Resource Pooling

Physical and virtual computing resources are pooled into the cloud. These resources are not dependent on location in the sense that the customer has no control nor has knowledge over their location.

5) AI, NLP and Data Mining on-the-go

Current cloud service providers such as Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform (GCP) offers Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing and Data Mining capabilities to harness insights from high volume of unstructured data as is the case for contents of social media

IV. CLOUD BASED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our proposed cloud architecture is based on a central system which can, i) publish policy related content to multiple social media let’s say SM_1 , SM_2 , ..., SM_n , simultaneously, ii) collect data on citizens’ interaction with them e.g., views, likes, comments, ratings, etc. in an efficient manner using the API of the targeted social media, and iii) make advanced processing in cloud in order to extract from them as much as possible useful information for the policy makers e.g., data analytics, visualization, sentiment analysis, simulation and forecasting.

Our cloud system enables the policy maker to develop an electronic political campaign on a public policy or agenda under discussion across multiple social media through a web-based dashboard, or through a mobile phone dashboard. For this purpose, a package of relevant social media content has to be created (e.g., short description, longer description, video, images, etc.), which will be distributed and published to multiple social media that attracts the groups of citizens that government wants to involve in the discussion.

According to the type of content, the content can be published in different social platforms e.g., the short description can be published in Twitter, the longer one in Facebook, videos in YouTube, images in Instagram, etc. The citizens will be able to access this content and interact with it (e.g., view it, like or dislike it, comment it). This system also enables the policy maker to retrieve information from all these social media data on users’ interaction with the content, and make advanced processing of them, both per social media platform and synthetically, in order to extract from them useful information for the policy maker. High-level view of the proposed architecture is shown in Fig 1.

The first layer (bottom of *Fig. 3*) will deal with the numerical interaction data to be retrieved from the social media, exploiting, and processing the ‘raw analytics’ which are provided by the analytics engines that nearly all social media have and make available to their users. The second layer (middle of *Fig. 3*) will deal with the textual interaction data to be retrieved from the social media (e.g., opinions, comments, critics etc.) and provide more advanced sentiment analytics. Finally, the third layer (shown in the top part of *Fig 3*) will provide simulation modelling feature that combines the raw and combined analytics from previous layers to generate information on the interest of public in published policy, acceptance by the society, critics, reviews, and future prediction on the result of this policy implementation, or even suggest different policy options.

V. PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

In this section we will discuss some preliminary findings concerning i) the capabilities provided by the APIs of the most popular social medias, ii) the value proposition of this approach, and iii) the pre-requirements for its practical application.

A. API Completeness and Limitations

We reviewed the API documentation of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube, the most popular social media at the time and tested them to gather data on social posts by government officials. We observed that there is a clear strategy of these social media to become more open and accessible to third party applications by conforming with open API standards (more details about this analysis and its conclusion are provided by Charalabidis, Gionis, & Loukis, 2015). In particular, through their APIs they provide a rich functionality for posting and retrieving content, exposing methods that go deeply into their innermost functionalities and provide third party developers with an ever-growing set of capabilities such as integrating their API with our proposed cloud based central system.

However, the APIs of most of the examined social media were not stable and changing frequently. They also do not provide two important fields, sex and age group, for each user interaction. e.g., view, comment, like, dislike, etc.; these fields are necessary for estimating awareness, interest and acceptance with respect to the policy under discussion, not only in total. Age and gender wise data for the posts would have been more practical for the decision maker to analyse and make informed decisions.

B. Value Proposition

A first investigation of the value generated by the proposed system was conducted through a series of interviews with experienced personnel from the Kathmandu Metropolitan City and especially Mayor Balen Shah IT Department Chief Mr. Nama Raj Dhakal. He mentioned that social media analysis provides the metro team with a low cost and efficient mechanism to better inform the policy decision process by considering the number of opinions and suggestions from wider and more diverse stakeholders’ groups across various social media. Similarly, Mrs, Sita Sharma, deputy director of IT Department at Kathmandu Metro mentions that the IT team is utilizing its social channel in Facebook to disseminate notice,

awareness, collect citizen feedback and opinions of various local matters. The Facebook page of Kathmandu Metro currently has 77,000 followers receiving over 1100 reactions and 40,000 reach on average on each post with. She added that Mayor Balen has additional plan in the future to bring in advanced social media analytics system to make informed decisions regarding matters of waste management, corruption reporting, complaints registry, ambulance infrastructure, and health car. When presented with our proposed architecture, the team at Kathmandu Metro were very promising and had a keen interest in integrating it to their official system given it is tested and fully developed. By giving policy makers a privileged interface for hearing society’s voice directly, where the public chooses to discuss and express its opinion, the proposed approach enables an innovative way to gather, evaluate and decide upon society’s input.

Furthermore, the capability to publish policy-related content from one single point to multiple social media and collection of insights from the same point results in time and cost efficiencies.

One thing to note is that such an electronic campaign may be launched during any of the phases of the policy making cycle (agenda setting, policy analysis, policy formulation, policy implementation, and policy monitoring and evaluation). The purpose, function and, as a consequence, value proposition of each campaign may vary according to the stage of the policy cycle in which the campaign is launched

C. Pre-Requirements

Despite all the benefits of such a cloud based central system for social media analysis, it does come with some requirements before it can be implemented. Firstly, it will require the creation of a new organizational unit to organize and manage the presence of the government agency in multiple social media platforms and also to analyse the large quantities of both structured data (e.g., citizens’ ratings) and unstructured data (e.g., citizens’ postings in textual form) that will be created and draw conclusions from them. Secondly, a cloud infrastructure is needed to setup as per the system architecture discussed earlier. This requires technical human resource with knowledge about these cloud platforms. Additionally, the human resources of these new units must have a particular culture and specialized skills for managing efficiently these new electronic modes of communication and highly sophisticated ICT-based tools.

VI. CASE STUDIES AND ANALYSIS

This study selects three case studies in Nepal to analyse the use of social media by government bodies and public in the context of policy making and national agenda. The data were mainly collected from public social media accounts, government social channels, news agenda social media accounts and government official accounts. These data were scrapped from the social media through their public REST API which is available to everyone and additionally with external software i.e., NVivo. Other data related to usage of social media in Nepal by citizens and officials is collected from a report by Nepal Administrative Staff College (Kirat Rai, Shyan & Tamang, Shital, 2022).

1) Balen Shah Mayor Campaign in Local Level Election 2022

Balen Shah was elected as the mayor of Kathmandu Metropolitan City on 30th May 2022 winning 38.6% of the votes casted (Republica, 2022). Since his announcement as a candidate on December 17, 2021 from his Facebook page. He has utilized his social media accounts better than any other candidates in the Nepal Local Election 2022. From raising awareness of his candidacy, releasing his public agendas to collecting citizen views on public policy, interacting with them, and collaborating with other politicians, Balen Shah social media usage can provide insightful data on the participation of public in government decision making and the potential of our proposed system.

TABLE I
ELECTION CAMPAIGN SOCIAL INTERACTION SINCE MARCH 2022

Areas	Likes	Comments	Share	Posts
Ask Vote	12.5m	41992	58021	31
Background Interviews	8.3m	20921	2819	11
Citizen Feedback	6.2m	39012	39282	15
Policy Discussion	10.2m	50210	41921	16
Metro Information	7.1m	10231	4819	20

As of 30th November 2022, Balen official social account has over 1.2 million on Facebook, 172,800 on Twitter and 215,000 on Instagram. Our analysis on his 92 posts (*Table 1*) since March across all three platforms shows, we found 31 posts were on related to asking votes for his mayoral candidacy for Kathmandu. Likewise, 11 posts related to his background interviews, 15 for citizen feedback topic, 16 for policy discussion and 20 related to metro information after his win. His posts on vote campaign gained the most reactions like 12.5 million likes, 41,992 comments and 58021 shares. We can also see that the post related to policy discussions gained the most comments over 50 thousand and 10.2 million likes. Background interviews, citizen feedback and metro information were the other popular post categories.

The data reflects that the public are interacting with government officials and Balen has used it well to communicate with them, collect feedbacks and discuss policies enabling public participation. Two hashtags #BalenForMayor and #AbaYuvaKoPalo were most prominent in his social posts reaching to audience of staggering 130 million across Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube and TikTok. We also found that waste management, removal of illegally built infrastructure and reducing corruption were the main talk points in his posts. From this study, we can see that people in Nepal are actively participating in social media in the topics on public interest and policy making giving a huge scope for the use of our cloud based central system architecture.

2) Ibike Alkmaar Campaign - Netherlands

We choose this study because the system used by the Alkmaar municipality is closest to the one proposed in our study. The only difference is the lack of use of central cloud computing system and instead relying on multiple independent manually provisioned IT infrastructure. The data on this study

can be useful to check the effective of our proposed central cloud system. The Ibike Alkmaar campaign was part of the 2016–2020 , in which local authorities attempted to maintain and stimulated a high level of bicycle use (Facebook profile of Ibike campaign in Alkmaar 2020). They wanted to reach out to the public of Alkmaar regarding its implementation, safety and parking concerns and key areas of focus

TABLE II
IBIKE ALKMAAR SOCIAL CAMPAGIN OVERVIEW

Posts Area	Likes	Comments	Share
Solution for bicycle parking	99	19	10
Improving attractiveness of cycling	28	179	4
Improving bicycle safety in neighbourhood	81	187	8
New bicycle routes	112	30	10
Improving bicycle safety	109	123	19

We collected the online data during September to October 2020 (*Table 2*). The municipality posted five messages on their Facebook account @ibikeAlkmaar. Within 22 days, there were 488 comments for the six posts. A web scraping tool- NVivo was used to extract data (e.g., messages posted by citizens) from the Facebook account. The total number of comments, likes, and shares for the five messages posted by the municipality were also collected.

The municipality also posted 208 reply comments and 64 likes in public responses. From public end, the most comments were given for bicycle safety, while the least comments were provided for the message about solutions for bicycle parking. There were also less comments for the message about new bicycle routes. This suggests that people paid more attention to current bicycle safety that affected their daily lives than solutions and planning new bicycle routes for the future. The analysis system at Alkmaar municipality processed all these data, and recommend the policy maker to improve existing safety standards in an around neighbourhood and to launch cycling campaign to invite more people to use cycling aa a mode of transport. This was passed by the city council in March 2021 (*Facebook profile of Ibike campaign in Alkmaar 2020*) and received a positive response from the citizen. Here, we can see that social media participation enabled citizens to have a higher level of accessibility and freedom than traditional participation method and that government utilized these data to make their decisions.

3) Citizens and Government Official e-readiness in Nepal with social media for policy making

Amidst all the benefits of our proposed system for social media analysis, it is important to also consider and analyse the current status of social media usage in Nepal by the citizens as well as the Government officials especially in the domain of agenda/policy making from local to national level. This is crucial because without the high penetration of citizens and policy makers in multiple social media platforms in the form of multiple content types, our system cannot generate accurate insights and may not fulfill its purpose.

TABLE III
E-READINESS DATA FOR NEPAL IN SOCIAL MEDIA

Description	Year	Face book	Insta-gram	Twitter	Link-edIn
Total Users	2021	10.1m	1.8m	0.31m	0.7m
Total Users	2022	12.3m	2.3m	0.41m	1m
Posts related to public policy	2020	21311	18923	19892	9281
Posts related to public policy	2021	27039	20849	21249	11021
Posts related to public policy	2022	39291	27320	29929	16829
Posts from Government Bodies and Officials related to public policy	2022	2391	1823	2102	1009
Aggregate Public Reactions on policy and government post	2022	15.9m	13.5m	12.6m	10.1m
% of Government units having social presence	2022	45%	5%	15%	1%

(Table III) displays the report from Kirat Rai, Shyan & Tamang, Shital. (2021) and Kemp, S. (2022) on the e-readiness of public and government bodies in social media for policy discussions across multiple platforms. We can see that there are more than 13.7m social media users in Nepal in 2022 with more than 20% rise than 2021. Social media posts related to public policy has increased from 21311 to 39291 in Facebook from 2020 to 2021. The growth is similar in Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn. We can clearly see that Facebook is the most used social media for such discussions followed by Twitter and Instagram and the least used is LinkedIn. In 2022, 45% of the government units had their social presence on Facebook. The aggregate reactions by the public on civic posts were 15.9 million in Facebook, 13.4 million on Instagram, 12.6 million on Instagram and 10.1 million on LinkedIn.

We can clearly see that social media usage is increasing rapidly in Nepal in recent years due to internet penetration. Likewise, government agencies, officials are creating their social presence and interacting with public on policy making matters. All of these also provides a great scope to our proposed architecture that can harness these data in cloud to generate insightful information and leads for the policy makers to make informed decisions and drive public participation.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The real-time, open characteristics and diverse nature make social media a powerful tool to engage a large number of participants and facilitate new forms of interactions between government and citizens. With ever increasing usage of social media in Nepal by the public and policy makers, it has become a platform for open discussion and for generating insightful information for driving decision making. This paper explores an advanced approach of exploiting social media by

government agencies in a systematic and centralized manner using a central cloud based system architecture. This helps in achieving a more intensive interaction with diverse groups of citizens, in order to promote and improve public participation in public policy making. This approach is based on a central cloud system, which enables i) publishing content of various types and to multiple social media simultaneously, ii) retrieving users' interactions with them (e.g., views, comments, likes) in all these social media, in an efficient. systematic and centrally managed automated manner using their APIs, and iii) performing advanced cloud processing of these interaction data using AI and data mining techniques, in order to extract as much possible useful information for supporting the policy making.

In particular, it has been concluded that the most popular social media have sufficient APIs for the technical implementation of the proposed approach, which provide a rich functionality for posting and retrieving content. However, there are some deficiencies of many social media APIs, such as lack of stability of them, and also lack of capabilities for retrieving some important demographics (e.g., sex, age group) for the retrieved content, which have negative consequences on the capabilities of the central cloud system. The architecture of the central system has been designed, a high-level view of it is shown in Figure 1, while the core units are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, which includes five interconnected cloud subsystems: web front-end, mobile native application and widget area, publishing, tracking, and storing content area, service discovery, composition and binding area, and decision support area. The research on the non-technical issues of the project including the interview series with Kathmandu Metropolitan City team has concluded that the proposed approach can definitely generate significant value both for government agencies and citizens. The three case studies: i) Balen Shah showed the rise of public participation in politics and decision-making, ii) Ibike Alkmaar campaign gave a comparative analysis on the effectiveness of our proposed system using the data of social media usage for bicycle campaign at Alkmaar city at Netherland and its impact for decision making, iii) e Readiness among Nepali public and officials showed that the social media usage is at all time high in Nepal and with this trend, our system can place an effective role in enabling public participation while helping the government to make informed decisions.

Further research is required for the implementation of architecture, validation, and evaluation (at the technological, organizational, and political level) of the proposed framework. In the next phase after implementation of our architecture, wide range of quantitative and qualitative techniques (e.g., focus group discussions, surveys and in-depth interview), will allow a deeper investigation and understanding of the value that this approach generates, and both the required improvement

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